

How Quakers' Beliefs in Monteverde, Costa Rica Impacted Conservation Practices

Phillip Davidson
HIST 596: Latin American History
Dr Joseph Lenti
8/16/2025

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Acknowledgements

I would like to express great gratitude to my professors Dr. Joseph Lenti, for his feedback and knowledge on Costa Rica, Dr. Julia Smith, chair of our department, who also helped guide me on this research while in Costa Rica, and Dr. Bill Youngs, national park expert, who also provided support during this research. Without them this research would have never happened.

I would also like to mention Aiden Graybeal, Quaker elder, and former Chaplain, who provided me support on the cultural sensitivity of researching the Religious Society of Friends.

Introduction

In the early 1950's, Quakers from Fairhope, Alabama moved to Monteverde, Costa Rica, fleeing the Korean War draft. Costa Rica, having abolished their military, served as the perfect asylum.¹ Erin Cavanagh in, "Monteverde, Costa Rica: Balancing Environment and Development", states, "The Quakers chose Costa Rica because Costa Rica's peaceful values matched their own."² This community of Quakers have had a major impact on Costa Rica, particularly in the way they interact with the land, through agricultural practices inspired by their faith and preservation of the Monteverde Cloudforest. Their values (called testimonies) helped curate their role in the region's development. If it were not for their pursuit of peace, a value very important in Quaker beliefs, they would have never arrived in Monteverde in the first place. With their values of community and integrity, they were able to foster good relations with local farmers who already knew about the land, as community is a big part of the Quaker faith. Their idea of stewardship is what really pushed for the preservation of land as they were farming with the locals, who shared similar beliefs. The ideals of the Quakers influenced their agricultural practices, community education, and overall land preservation.

Testimonies of the Religious Society of Friends

The Religious Society of Friends (Quakers) have 5 core beliefs, called "testimonies": Simplicity, Peace, Integrity, Community, Equality, Stewardship, often referred to by the acronym "SPICES."³ These values, shared by the members, are foundational for understanding the way the Quakers interacted with the land. For instance, the testimony of peace brought the Quakers to

¹ Shragai, Atalia. Cold War paradise: Settlement, culture, and identity-making among US Americans in Costa Rica, 1945–1980. *U of Nebraska Press*, 2022.

² Cavanagh, Erin. "Monteverde, Costa Rica: Balancing Environment and Development." *Monteverde Institute* (2005): 1-18.

³ Cox, Tom. "Integrity — Seeds | Semillas — #21 January 2024." *Seeds*, February 8, 2024. <https://seedsmfm.org/integrity-seeds-semillas-21-january-2024/>.

Costa Rica; they saw Costa Rica as a peaceful country.⁴ As the Monteverde Monthly Meeting of Friends Book of Discipline states, “They felt they could best do their individual part toward building for a peaceful world by seeking an environment as free as possible from militarism in which to live and rear their children.”⁵ The testimony of “community” brought them to collaborate with the *campesinos* (local farmers), as they shared many similar beliefs about sustainable farming and preservation.⁶ Arguably the most relevant of the group’s values that influenced Monteverde would be “stewardship.” In “The development of ecospirituality among British Quakers,” Peter Collins states, “...One Friend stood and quoted from Quaker Faith and Practice, emphasising the point that we are stewards of the natural environment and should do what we could to protect it.”⁷ This is in reference to a Friends meeting in the British Isles, where they were discussing re-designing their meeting house garden.⁸ The re-design for the garden would make it much better for the local ecology, helping local plants and wildlife; however, to do this they would have to remove part of the old garden.⁹ Some of the Quakers in the meeting believed that they should not dig up what is already a good garden; the Friend that stood and stated the quote about being stewards did not want to do the re-design for that reason.¹⁰ The

⁴ Chase, Sophie. "Collaborating with the Monteverde Community Fund to Develop a Plan for Youth Programs in Monteverde, Costa Rica." PhD diss., *Worcester Polytechnic Institute*, 2021.

⁵ Monteverde Monthly Meeting of Friends. “Discipline of Monteverde Monthly Meeting of Friends.” *Discipline of Monteverde Monthly Meeting of Friends*, June 13, 2021. https://monteverdequakers.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Discipline_2021_06_June_13.pdf.

⁶ Chase, Sophie. "Collaborating with the Monteverde Community Fund to Develop a Plan for Youth Programs in Monteverde, Costa Rica." PhD diss., *Worcester Polytechnic Institute*, 2021.

⁷ Collins, Peter Jeffrey. "The development of ecospirituality among British Quakers." *Ecozon@: European Journal of Literature, Culture and Environment* 2, no. 2 (2011).

⁸ Collins, Peter Jeffrey. "The development of ecospirituality among British Quakers." *Ecozon@: European Journal of Literature, Culture and Environment* 2, no. 2 (2011).

⁹ Collins, Peter Jeffrey. "The development of ecospirituality among British Quakers." *Ecozon@: European Journal of Literature, Culture and Environment* 2, no. 2 (2011).

¹⁰ Collins, Peter Jeffrey. "The development of ecospirituality among British Quakers." *Ecozon@: European Journal of Literature, Culture and Environment* 2, no. 2 (2011).

emphasis that this meeting placed on deliberate and intentional decision making is reflective of the Quaker community as a whole.

Arrival of Quakers and their Practices

When the Alabama Quakers first arrived in Monteverde, they acquired 1500 hectares of land and divided it among the families, each family building their own house.¹¹ They set up tents that they had brought from the United States. Atalia Shragai in “Cold War paradise: Settlement, culture, and identity-making among US Americans in Costa Rica, 1945–1980,” states, “The Quakers who in 1953 established Monteverde first lived in tents they had brought over from the United States, and later in thatched-roof “shacks,” as they called them, which were similar to ranchos.”¹² This settlement strategy would influence their unique farming methods and land development practices.

One of the most notable aspects of the Quakers’ that moved to Monteverde in the 1950’s were their agricultural practices. Shragai states, “In the first year of its establishment in the early 1950s, the Quaker colony in Monteverde was rather isolated and thus reliant on the Costa Ricans from nearby communities.”¹³ ¹⁴ These local farmers, or “*campesinos*,” from nearby communities, helped share their knowledge of land and their current practices.¹⁵ This led to the culture of Monteverde having a mixture of beliefs from, with the Quakers and the *campesinos* sharing the land, as Sophie Chase states, “The culture of Monteverde was a blend of Quaker and *campesino* beliefs, which consisted of a desire for volunteerism, collaboration, self-governance, and public

¹¹ Quakers in the World. “Quakers in Costa Rica,” n.d.

¹² Shragai, Atalia. Cold War paradise: Settlement, culture, and identity-making among US Americans in Costa Rica, 1945–1980. *U of Nebraska Press*, 2022.

¹³ Shragai, Atalia. Cold War paradise: Settlement, culture, and identity-making among US Americans in Costa Rica, 1945–1980. *U of Nebraska Press*, 2022.

¹⁴ Cavanagh, Erin. "Monteverde, Costa Rica: Balancing Environment and Development." *Monteverde Institute* (2005): 1-18.

¹⁵ Chase, Sophie. "Collaborating with the Monteverde Community Fund to Develop a Plan for Youth Programs in Monteverde, Costa Rica." *Worcester Polytechnic Institute*, 2021.

conversation” in “Collaborating with the Monteverde Community Fund to Develop a Plan for Youth Programs in Monteverde, Costa Rica.”¹⁶ The Quakers and *campesinos*, while culturally different, shared very similar belief systems that helped foster Monteverde’s environment of sustainable farming, and preservation and the locals were influenced by the ideals of Quakers. As Colby Nixon states, “American Quaker emigrants aided in the development of conservation methods in the region by evangelizing locals with the dual ideas of the Quaker faith and later of conservation.”¹⁷ As shown, the Quaker belief of community helped them foster an innovative environment with the locals, and ultimately furthered advancement of the preservation of the land. The Quakers set aside the land for a private cloud forest reserve, to help preserve their drinking water.

Cultural Clashes

The Quakers had to adapt to the new environment and regional culinary practices. Shragai adds, “Dorothy Rockwell, who was among the founders of the colony, described how she and the other women “adapted” the recipes they knew from their homes in the U.S. American Deep South to what they could grow in Costa Rica.” For example, many staple foods like apples are non-native to Costa Rica.¹⁸ As Shragai states, “Quaker women yearned for substitutes for their applesauce and cakes, especially around Christmas time.”¹⁹ They used a common Costa Rican vegetable, the chayote, as a substitute for apples.²⁰

¹⁶ Chase, Sophie. "Collaborating with the Monteverde Community Fund to Develop a Plan for Youth Programs in Monteverde, Costa Rica." *Worcester Polytechnic Institute*, 2021.

¹⁷ Nixon, Colby. "A Review Examining the Factors Contributory to the Socialization of a Culture of Environmental Stewardship." (2025).

¹⁸ Shragai, Atalia. *Cold War paradise: Settlement, culture, and identity-making among US Americans in Costa Rica, 1945–1980*. *U of Nebraska Press*, 2022.

¹⁹ Shragai, Atalia. *Cold War paradise: Settlement, culture, and identity-making among US Americans in Costa Rica, 1945–1980*. *U of Nebraska Press*, 2022.

²⁰ Shragai, Atalia. *Cold War paradise: Settlement, culture, and identity-making among US Americans in Costa Rica, 1945–1980*. *U of Nebraska Press*, 2022.

While the Quakers came to Costa Rica to farm (and for peace), the Quaker faith value of “stewardship” contributed to the Monteverde community’s commitment to conservation. As Cavanagh states, “Quakers wanted to live simply by farming and producing dairy products.”²¹ While conservation was not the main goal of the Quakers, it was a side effect of their stewardship principles. Quakers would practice a variety of conservation techniques in conjunction with their farming.²² Cavanagh states that some of these would be, “saving forested areas, allowing natural windbreaks to regenerate, and planting trees in pastured areas.”²³ The Quakers value ethical consumption and condemn luxury.²⁴ This goes into both their ideas of stewardship and simplicity. Quakers have had a long history of environmentalism and ethical use of the land, since the mid-seventeenth century.²⁵ From 1650-1750, Quakers started to implement a system of discipline justified from Biblical text, for the “do’s and don’ts” of the aspects of life.²⁶ This system of discipline would determine what Quakers could own or not own, and how they consumed commodities of all kinds.²⁷

The Quakers in Monteverde also placed emphasis on education, educating many Quakers and locals for approximately 50 years.²⁸ In Laureen Fregeau’s “Progressive Education and Quaker Schooling: Alabama Emigrants' Influence on Education in Monte Verde, Costa Rica,”

²¹ Cavanagh, Erin. "Monteverde, Costa Rica: Balancing Environment and Development." *Monteverde Institute* (2005): 1-18.

²² Cavanagh, Erin. "Monteverde, Costa Rica: Balancing Environment and Development." *Monteverde Institute* (2005): 1-18.

²³ Cavanagh, Erin. "Monteverde, Costa Rica: Balancing Environment and Development." *Monteverde Institute* (2005): 1-18.

²⁴ Collins, Peter Jeffrey. "The development of ecospirituality among British Quakers." *Ecozon@: European Journal of Literature, Culture and Environment* 2, no. 2 (2011).

²⁵ Collins, Peter Jeffrey. "The development of ecospirituality among British Quakers." *Ecozon@: European Journal of Literature, Culture and Environment* 2, no. 2 (2011).

²⁶ Collins, Peter Jeffrey. "The development of ecospirituality among British Quakers." *Ecozon@: European Journal of Literature, Culture and Environment* 2, no. 2 (2011).

²⁷ Collins, Peter Jeffrey. "The development of ecospirituality among British Quakers." *Ecozon@: European Journal of Literature, Culture and Environment* 2, no. 2 (2011).

²⁸ Fregeau, Laureen A., Robert D. Leier, and Joseph W. Newman. "Progressive Education and Quaker Schooling: Alabama Emigrants' Influence on Education in Monte Verde, Costa Rica." *The High School Journal* 84, no. 1 (2000): 14-25.

Fregeau states, “For almost fifty years the Monteverde Friends School has offered Quaker and Tican (native Costa Rican) students an education that reflects Marietta Johnson's "organic" idea: ‘The school program, to be educational, must be life-giving to body, mind, and spirit - the complete organism.’”²⁹ This idea that education is organic and made for organisms comes from Marietta Johnson Quaker School of Organic Education in Fairhope, Alabama, or the also known as the “Organic School”.³⁰ Quakers took ideas from the Organic School and eventually brought them to Monteverde.³¹ The Monteverde Friends School teaches using the Montessori teaching method, and views teachers more as guides to the students, helping them navigate and focusing on quality over quantity.³² They teach in groups of mixed ages, as the students will be able to not only learn from the teachers but also from each other.³³ Even the school itself was built with sustainability in mind, with reusing building materials, harvesting rain water and water treatment as well as a windmill and solar panel system.³⁴

²⁹ Fregeau, Lauren A., Robert D. Leier, and Joseph W. Newman. "Progressive Education and Quaker Schooling: Alabama Emigrants' Influence on Education in Monte Verde, Costa Rica." *The High School Journal* 84, no. 1 (2000): 14-25.

³⁰ Fregeau, Lauren A., Robert D. Leier, and Joseph W. Newman. "Progressive Education and Quaker Schooling: Alabama Emigrants' Influence on Education in Monte Verde, Costa Rica." *The High School Journal* 84, no. 1 (2000): 14-25.

³¹ Fregeau, Lauren A., Robert D. Leier, and Joseph W. Newman. "Progressive Education and Quaker Schooling: Alabama Emigrants' Influence on Education in Monte Verde, Costa Rica." *The High School Journal* 84, no. 1 (2000): 14-25.

³² Graff, Linsey, Brian Moran, Fernando Santana, Tyler Stanley, Oriane Daley, Daniel Dimillo, and Brian Hettler. "The Monteverde Friends School, 2009."

³³ Graff, Linsey, Brian Moran, Fernando Santana, Tyler Stanley, Oriane Daley, Daniel Dimillo, and Brian Hettler. "The Monteverde Friends School, 2009."

³⁴ Graff, Linsey, Brian Moran, Fernando Santana, Tyler Stanley, Oriane Daley, Daniel Dimillo, and Brian Hettler. "The Monteverde Friends School, 2009."

Conclusion

It is clear that the beliefs of Quakers in Costa Rica greatly influenced the Monteverde region, their values of Simplicity, Peace, Integrity, Community, Equality, and Stewardship all played a role in the region's development and the preservation of the Monteverde Cloud Forest. Simplicity, living of life without luxury pushed by a desire for community and inclusivity helped Monteverde come to what it is today. Quakers taking consumption of resources seriously and their desire to be sustainable and steward the environment helped preserve what is the Monteverde Cloud Forest. With help from the local *campesinos*, Quakers were able to foster an inclusive community which mutually benefited the Quakers, the locals, and the land.

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